

Comparison of Cognitive Function In Adults Aged 65 and Over Engaged and Not Engaged In Formal Volunteering In Non-Governmental Organizations:

Engin PÜLLÜM¹, Çağdaş AKGÜLLÜ², Fatma TAŞKIN^{1*}

¹Aydın State Hospital, Physiotherapy and Rehabilitation Unit, Aydın, Türkiye

²Adnan Menderes University Faculty of Medicine, Department of Cardiology, Aydın, Türkiye

*Sorumlu yazar: fatos_taskin09@hotmail.com

Abstract

This study aimed to compare cognitive function, depression levels, and selected physical performance parameters among adults aged 65 years and older who were engaged in formal volunteering in non-governmental organizations (NGOs) and those who were not. In addition, the study sought to evaluate the potential contribution of volunteering activities to cognitive and physical health outcomes in older adults. This cross-sectional comparative study included a total of 107 adults aged 65 years and older. Participants were divided into two groups: formal volunteers (Group 2, n=37) and non-volunteers (Group 1, n=70). Data were collected using the Standardized Mini-Mental Test (SMMT) to assess cognitive function, the Geriatric Depression Scale (GDS) to evaluate depressive symptoms, handgrip strength measurements, a 6-meter timed up-and-go test, anthropometric measurements, and a structured questionnaire developed by the researchers. Descriptive statistics, chi-square tests, independent samples t-tests, Mann–Whitney U tests, Kruskal–Wallis tests, and correlation analyses were used to analyze the data. The mean years of education were significantly higher in the formal volunteer group (12.54 years) than in the non-volunteer group (8.34 years) ($p<0.001$). No statistically significant difference was found between the groups in terms of cognitive function scores ($p=0.231$). However, significant differences were observed in timed up-and-go test performance and GDS scores ($p<0.001$ for both). Correlation analyses revealed a significant positive association between waist circumference and cognitive function scores in both groups. Furthermore, handgrip strength was significantly associated with cognitive function only in the formal volunteer group. No significant difference in cognitive function was identified between older adults engaged in formal volunteering and those who were not. Nevertheless, formal volunteers demonstrated lower levels of depression and better physical performance. These findings suggest that participation in volunteering activities may contribute positively to psychological well-being and physical functioning in older adults and may represent a valuable strategy for promoting healthy aging.

Keywords: Cognitive function, Depression, Physical performance, Volunteering, Elderly

Sivil Toplum Kuruluşlarında Gönüllü Olarak Çalışan ve Çalışmayan 65 Yaş ve Üzeri Bireylerde Bilişsel Fonksiyonların Karşılaştırılması

Özet

Bu çalışma, sivil toplum kuruluşlarında gönüllü olarak çalışan ve çalışmayan 65 yaş ve üzeri bireylerde bilişsel fonksiyon, depresyon düzeyi ve bazı fiziksel performans parametrelerini karşılaştırmak amacıyla yapılmıştır. Ayrıca gönüllülük faaliyetlerine katılımın yaşlı bireylerin bilişsel ve fiziksel sağlık göstergeleri üzerindeki olası etkilerinin değerlendirilmesi amaçlanmıştır. Kesitsel ve karşılaştırmalı tipteki bu araştırmaya 65 yaş ve üzeri toplam 107 birey dahil edilmiştir. Katılımcılar gönüllü olarak çalışanlar (Grup 2, n=37) ve gönüllü olarak çalışmayanlar (Grup 1, n=70) olmak üzere iki gruba ayrılmıştır. Veriler, bilişsel fonksiyonları değerlendirmek amacıyla Standardize Mini Mental Test (SMMT), depresif belirtileri değerlendirmek amacıyla Geriatrik Depresyon Ölçeği (GDS), el kavrama kuvveti ölçümü, 6 metre zamanlı kalk-yürü testi, antropometrik ölçümler ve araştırmacılar tarafından geliştirilen yapılandırılmış bir anket aracılığıyla toplanmıştır. Verilerin analizinde tanımlayıcı istatistikler, ki-kare testi, bağımsız örneklem t-testi, Mann–Whitney U testi, Kruskal–Wallis testi ve korelasyon analizleri kullanılmıştır. Resmi gönüllü grupta ortalama eğitim süresi (12,54 yıl), gönüllü olmayan gruba (8,34 yıl) göre anlamlı düzeyde daha yüksek bulunmuştur ($p<0,001$). Gruplar arasında bilişsel fonksiyon puanları açısından istatistiksel olarak anlamlı bir farklılık saptanmamıştır ($p=0,231$). Buna karşın zamanlı kalk-yürü testi ve GDS puanları açısından gruplar arasında istatistiksel olarak anlamlı farklılıklar belirlenmiştir (her ikisi için $p<0,001$). Korelasyon analizlerinde bel çevresi ile bilişsel fonksiyon puanları arasında her iki grupta da anlamlı pozitif ilişki bulunmuştur. El kavrama kuvveti ile bilişsel fonksiyon arasındaki anlamlı ilişki ise yalnızca gönüllü grupta saptanmıştır. Gönüllü olarak çalışan ve çalışmayan yaşlı bireyler arasında bilişsel fonksiyon açısından anlamlı bir fark bulunmamıştır. Bununla birlikte gönüllü bireylerin depresyon düzeylerinin daha düşük ve fiziksel performanslarının daha iyi olduğu belirlenmiştir. Bulgular, gönüllülük faaliyetlerinin yaşlı bireylerde psikolojik iyilik hali ve fiziksel fonksiyonların desteklenmesine katkı sağlayabileceğini düşündürmektedir.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Bilişsel fonksiyon, Depresyon, Fiziksel performans, Gönüllülük, Yaşlı

INTRODUCTION

Engaging in mentally stimulating activities and maintaining cognitive engagement are considered key factors in successful cognitive aging (Cruz-Jentoft et al., 2010). There is growing evidence that formal volunteering is associated with higher levels of subjective well-being in later life. Participation in voluntary activities within non-governmental organizations is thought to contribute to continuous learning and help maintain both mental and physical activity (Pilkington, Windsor, & Crisp, 2012).

Several mechanisms may explain the beneficial effects of formal volunteering on mental health, particularly among older adults. Volunteering provides access to social and psychological resources that can help mitigate negative outcomes such as depression and anxiety. An analysis of three waves of data from the *Changing Lives Dataset* (1986, 1989, 1994) demonstrated that volunteering reduced depression levels in individuals aged 65 and over, and that long-term engagement in volunteering provided cognitive benefits for both men and women. It has been suggested that part of the positive effect of volunteering on depression in older adults may be explained by increased social participation (Musick & Wilson, 2003).

Comparisons between older and younger volunteers have shown that older individuals experience greater improvements in life satisfaction and perceived health over time (Van Willigen, 2000). Furthermore, participation in formal volunteering has been associated with a 44% reduction in mortality compared to non-participation. A curvilinear relationship has also been identified between the number of hours spent in volunteering activities and mortality outcomes (Musick & Wilson, 2003).

Findings from a twenty-year cohort study indicate a positive association between environmental volunteering and health outcomes. Individuals engaged in environmental volunteering reported higher levels of physical activity, better overall health, and fewer depressive symptoms (Pillemer et al., 2010). Despite this growing body of evidence, relatively few studies have examined the combined effects of formal volunteering on health outcomes, highlighting the need for further research in this area (Chang et al., 2022).

This study aimed to compare cognitive function, depression levels, and selected physical parameters in adults aged 65 years and older who are engaged in formal volunteering in non-governmental organizations (NGOs) and those who are not.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study Design and Setting

This study was designed as a cross-sectional comparative study conducted to compare cognitive function, depression, and selected physical parameters in individuals aged 65 years and older who were engaged and not engaged in formal volunteering in non-governmental organizations.

The study was carried out in the central district of Aydin, Türkiye, which has the highest population density and the greatest number of active non-governmental organizations in the region. Aydin is also one of the cities with a relatively high proportion of older adults. The total population of Aydin is 1,134,031, with older adults comprising 14.1% of the population. In the central district, the population is 300,225, and the proportion of older adults is approximately 16%, corresponding to around 48,036 individuals (TUIK, 2021).

Participants

The study sample consisted of individuals aged 65 years and older who had no neurological diagnosis and were able to walk independently and perform basic daily activities

without assistance. Participants were divided into two groups: those engaged in formal volunteering (Group 2) in non-governmental organizations and those who were not (Group 1).

Group 1 consisted of 70 individuals aged 65 years and older, living in the same region, without a neurological diagnosis, able to walk independently, and not engaged in formal volunteering. Participants in this group were selected from the same socio-demographic environment as the volunteer group.

Group 2 initially included 51 individuals registered in 21 non-governmental organizations in the study region, of whom 37 agreed to participate in the study. The participation rate was calculated as 72.5%.

Sampling Method

Participants in Group 1 were identified using the snowball sampling method. For Group 2, simple random sampling was used since all eligible individuals had an equal probability of being included in the study.

Data Collection

Data collection was conducted between March 2021 and January 2022, during which a total of 107 participants were included in the study. Data were collected using interview and measurement techniques, with each session lasting approximately 20–30 minutes.

All data were collected through face-to-face interviews conducted by the researcher. Cognitive function was first assessed using the Standardized Mini-Mental Test (SMMT). Participants with scores below 24 were excluded from further data collection. Data collection was completed only for participants who met the inclusion criteria and scored 24 or higher on the SMMT.

Both verbal and written informed consent were obtained from all participants prior to participation.

Measures

Personal Information Form

The personal information form was used to assess socio-demographic characteristics, including age, education level, marital status, income, and health-related behaviors.

Cognitive Function

The Standardized Mini-Mental Test (SMMT), originally developed in 1975 and later standardized by Molloy and Standish in 1997, was used to assess cognitive function (Molloy & Standish, 1997). The test evaluates multiple cognitive domains, including orientation, short- and long-term memory, attention and calculation, motor function, perception, recall, language, and visuospatial abilities. It consists of three sections and is scored out of a total of 30 points.

Scores between 24 and 30 are considered normal, scores between 18 and 23 indicate mild cognitive impairment, and scores of 17 or below indicate severe cognitive impairment. The SMMT is widely used as a practical and reliable tool for screening and clinical follow-up. Its validity and reliability in the Turkish population were established by Güngen et al. (Güngen et al., 2002), and the cut-off value for dementia was reported as 23/24 points.

Depression

Depressive symptoms were assessed using the Geriatric Depression Scale (GDS), developed by Yesavage et al. (Yesavage et al., 1982). The scale consists of simple yes/no questions designed for older adults and excludes physical symptoms that may be related to conditions other than depression, such as sleep disturbances or somatic complaints. Each response indicative of depression is scored as one point. The Turkish validity and reliability of

the scale have been confirmed in previous studies (Ertan, Eker, & Şar, 1997; Sağduyu, 1997). In this study, the 15-item version of the GDS was used.

Physical and Anthropometric Measurements

Anthropometric measurements were obtained to evaluate factors potentially associated with cognitive function, including body mass index (BMI) and waist circumference. Physical performance was assessed through handgrip strength and walking speed.

Handgrip strength was measured using a calibrated digital hand dynamometer (Takei T.K.K. 5401, Yokohama, Japan). Participants stood with their dominant arm flexed at the elbow and held parallel to the ground. After one practice trial, three maximal grip attempts were recorded, and the highest value was used for analysis (Taekema et al., 2010).

Ethical Considerations

Ethical approval for this study was obtained from Aydin Adnan Menderes University Ethics Committee (Approval No: 2019/60, Date: 09/05/2019). All procedures were conducted in accordance with the principles of the Declaration of Helsinki.

Statistical Analysis

Statistical analyses were performed using SPSS (Statistical Package for the Social Sciences) version 26 (SPSS Inc., Chicago, IL, USA). Descriptive statistical methods were used to evaluate the data. Continuous variables were expressed as mean \pm standard deviation, while categorical variables were presented as frequencies and percentages.

The chi-square test was used to compare categorical variables between independent groups. The Kolmogorov–Smirnov test was applied to assess the normality of data distribution. When the assumptions for parametric tests were met, the independent samples t-test was used to compare differences between groups. When these assumptions were not met, the Mann–Whitney U test was used. A 95% confidence interval was adopted, and a p-value of < 0.05 was considered statistically significant. For chi-square analysis, participants' subjective health perception, originally categorized into five groups ('very good', 'good', 'moderate', 'bad', and 'very bad'), was reclassified into two categories to ensure more reliable analysis. 'Very good' and 'good' responses were combined as 'good', while 'moderate', 'bad', and 'very bad' responses were grouped as 'poor'.

RESULTS

For Group 2, 51 individuals aged 65 years and older who met the inclusion criteria and were engaged in formal volunteering in non-governmental organizations were identified. Of these, 13 declined to participate, and complete data could not be obtained from one participant. Therefore, data from 37 individuals were included in the analysis.

For Group 1, 82 individuals with similar socio-demographic characteristics were identified, and complete data were obtained from 70 participants. In total, data from 37 participants in Group 2 (formal volunteers) and 70 participants in Group 1 (non-volunteers) were analyzed.

The comparison of socio-demographic characteristics between the groups is presented in Table 1. Statistically significant differences were observed in age, gender, and years of education ($p < 0.05$). No significant differences were found in marital status, income level, reading glasses use, subjective health perception, regular reading habits, or living arrangement ($p > 0.05$) (Table 1).

Table 1. Comparison of Socio-demographic Characteristics of Participants

		Group 2 (n:37)		Group 1 (n:70)		Total			
Socio-demographic characteristics		N	%	n	%	χ^2	p	n	%
Age	65-74	31	83.7	59	84.3	26.38	0.04*	90	84.1
	75 and above	6	16.3	11	15.7			17	16.9
Gender	Female	24	64.8	4	5.7	40.82	0.00*	28	26.2
	Male	13	35.2	66	94.3			79	73.8
Marital status	Married	23	62.1	53	85.7	1.55	0.14	76	71.0
	Single	14	37.9	17	24.3			31	29.0
Education	1-5 years	1	2.7	27	38.5	42.04	0.00*	28	26.2
	6-11 years	14	37.8	30	42.8			44	41.1
	12+ years	22	59.5	13	18.7			35	32.7
Income level	Fair/good	31	83.7	49	70.0	6.44	0.40	80	74.7
	Low	6	16.3	21	30.0			27	25.3
Reading glasses	Yes	33	89.1	63	90.0	1.00	0.56	96	89.7
	None	4	20.9	7	10.0			11	10.3
Subjective health perception	Very good-Fair	35	94.6	65	92.8	8.69	0.34	100	93.4
	Bad	2	5.4	5	7.2			7	6.6
Regular reading	Yes	29	78.4	43	71.4	2.43	0.11	72	67.3
	No	8	21.2	27	28.6			35	32.7
Who do you live with?	Spouse/child	25	67.6	56	80	4.58	0.20	81	72.18
	Alone	12	32.4	14	20			26	27.82

Group 1: Non- volunteers, Group 2: Formal volunteers. χ^2 : Chi-square test. * $p < 0.05$

The comparison of participants' lifestyle characteristics is presented in Table 2. There were statistically significant differences between the groups in subjective health perception and hearing aid use ($p < 0.05$). No statistically significant differences were found between the groups in smoking/alcohol use, use of glasses, regular reading, paid employment, regular walking, social participation, and caregiving status ($p > 0.05$) (Table 2).

Table 2. Comparison of Findings Regarding the Lifestyle and Health Characteristics of the Participants

Group 1: Non-volunteers, Group 2: Formal volunteers. χ^2 : Chi-square test. dof: degrees of freedom. * $p < 0.05$

Life Habits		Group 2 (n:37)		Group 1 (n:70)		χ^2	dof	P
		n	%	n	%			
Smoking	Yes	6	13.5	13	18.6	0.443	1	0.506
	No	31	86.5	57	81.4			
Alcohol	Yes	10	27	12	17.1	1.448	1	0.229
	No	27	73	58	82.9			
Reading glasses	Yes	33	89.2	63	90	0.017	1	0.075
	No	4	10.8	7	10			
Regular reading	Yes	29	78.4	43	61.4	3.159	1	0.075
	No	8	21.6	27	38.6			
Working status	Yes	2	5.4	2	2.9	0.437	1	0.509
	No	35	94.6	68	97.1			
Social participation	Yes	36	97.3	68	97.1	0.02	1	1.000
	No	1	2.7	2	2.9			
Active caregiving	Yes	19	51.4	27	38.6	1.613	1	0.204
	No	18	48.6	43	61.4			

Subjective health perception	Good/very good	30	81.1	37	52.8	8.237	1	0.040*
	Bad/very bad	7	18.9	33	47.2			
Hearing aid	Yes	6	16.2	2	2.86	6.245	1	0.020*
	No	31	83.8	68	97.14			

The correlations between health-related characteristics and cognitive function scores in both groups are presented in Table 3. A statistically significant positive correlation was observed between waist circumference and cognitive function scores in both groups ($p < 0.05$). In addition, handgrip strength was significantly positively correlated with cognitive function scores only in the formal volunteer group (Group 2) ($p = 0.004$). No statistically significant correlations were found between cognitive function scores and timed walk test, GDS score, BMI, number of medications, or number of chronic diseases in either group ($p > 0.05$) (Table 3).

Table 3. Correlations Between Health Characteristics and Cognitive Function Scores in Formal Volunteers and Non-Volunteers

Independent Variables	Cognitive function level (SMMT) Group 2 (n:37)		Cognitive function level (SMMT) Group 1 (n:70)	
	R	p	r	p
Timed walk test (s)	-.086	0.480 ^b	-.043	0.802 ^b
GDS Score	-.007	0.952 ^b	-.152	0.368 ^b
Grip strength (N)	.336	0.004^{a*}	.300	0.072 ^a
BMI Score (kg/m ²)	.164	0.174 ^a	.209	0.214 ^a
Waist circumference (cm)	.290	0.015^{a*}	.334	0.043^{a*}
Medication (number)	-.054	0.657 ^b	.007	0.966 ^b
Chronic disease (number)	.040	0.743 ^b	.006	0.971 ^b

SMMT: Standardized Mini-Mental Test. GDS: Geriatric Depression Scale. BMI: Body Mass Index. a: pearson. b: spearman. * $p < 0.05$

The correlations between socio-demographic characteristics and cognitive function scores are presented in Table 4. No statistically significant correlations were found between socio-demographic variables and cognitive function scores in either Group 1 or Group 2 ($p > 0.05$) (Table 4).

Table 4. Correlations Between Socio-demographic Characteristics and Cognitive Function Scores of Participants

Group	Independent Variables	Cognitive function level (SMMT)	
		r	P
Group 2 (n:37)	Age (year)	-.219	0.069 ^b
	Education (year)	.075	0.540 ^b
Group 1 (n:70)	Age (year)	.101	0.552 ^b
	Education (year)	-.070	0.679 ^b

SMMT: Standardized Mini-Mental Test. b: spearman. * $p < 0.05$

DISCUSSION

This study compared cognitive function, depression, and physical performance between older adults engaged in formal volunteering in non-governmental organizations and those who were not. The findings demonstrated that there was no statistically significant difference in cognitive function between the two groups. However, individuals engaged in formal volunteering exhibited lower levels of depression and better physical performance compared to their non-volunteering counterparts.

No significant differences were observed between the groups in terms of income level, marital status, number of chronic diseases, or number of medications used. These findings suggest that the two groups were largely comparable in terms of general health and socio-demographic characteristics.

Previous studies have consistently reported that formal volunteers tend to be wealthier, better educated, and healthier than non-volunteers (Pilkington et al., 2012; Infurna, Okun, & Grimm, 2016; Matthews & Nazroo, 2021). Similarly, in the present study, the education level of the formal volunteer group was significantly higher than that of the non-volunteer group ($p < 0.001$). This may be explained by the fact that individuals with higher educational attainment often have better socioeconomic conditions and are therefore more likely to participate in voluntary activities in later life.

Some studies have reported that cognitive function is higher in individuals who remain actively engaged in work or volunteering during middle and older ages, with stronger effects observed in women (Infurna et al., 2016; Kim, 2016). In addition, longitudinal studies have shown that cognitive function and independence in activities of daily living are important determinants of mortality risk (Gao et al., 2014). Higher education has also been associated with greater cognitive reserve and a reduced risk of cognitive decline. Furthermore, increased physical, social, and cognitive activity has been shown to contribute to improved cognitive and neurological health in older adults (Han et al., 2020; Luoh & Herzog, 2002).

Despite these findings, no significant difference in cognitive function was observed between the groups in this study. One possible explanation is that participants in both groups maintained relatively active lifestyles. In particular, the non-volunteer group was also socially active and engaged in regular physical activity, which may have contributed to preserving cognitive function. Additionally, the relatively young age range of the participants (65–74 years) may explain the absence of cognitive differences. Cultural factors, such as strong family ties and social engagement in Turkish society, may also play a role in maintaining cognitive function in older adults. Recent evidence has continued to support a potential association between volunteering and cognitive health in later life. A longitudinal analysis of the Health and Retirement Study reported that volunteering may contribute to the maintenance of cognitive functioning through increased cognitive, social, and physical activity. Similarly, studies conducted among community-dwelling older adults have suggested that participation in volunteer activities is associated with better cognitive functioning and greater engagement in cognitively stimulating activities. However, these beneficial effects may become more apparent over longer follow-up periods and may not always be detectable in cross-sectional studies such as the present one (Villalonga-Olives et al., 2023; Guiney et al., 2021).

Consistent with the literature, depression scores were significantly lower in the formal volunteer group. Participation in volunteering activities may provide psychological benefits through increased social interaction, a sense of purpose, and engagement in meaningful activities. These findings support the view that volunteering plays an important role in promoting mental well-being in older adults. These findings are also supported by more recent studies demonstrating that volunteering is associated with improved psychological well-being, greater purpose in life, and better self-rated health among older adults. Participation in meaningful volunteer roles may strengthen resilience and social connectedness, thereby

contributing to lower depressive symptoms and improved overall well-being in later life (Lee et al., 2021; Jiang et al., 2021).

Handgrip strength is considered an important indicator of frailty and functional capacity in older adults and has been associated with cognitive decline (Kim, 2016). In the present study, the mean handgrip strength values in both groups were above the threshold values defined for sarcopenia. This finding may be explained by the relatively young age and preserved functional independence of the participants. Although no significant difference in grip strength was observed between the groups, this may be explained by the overall good physical condition of both groups.

Walking speed is another important marker of both physical and cognitive health (Pasma et al., 2014). Previous studies have shown that physical activity, including aerobic exercise, can positively influence cognitive function and brain structure in older adults (Yaffe et al., 2009; Carvalho et al., 2014). In the present study, a statistically significant difference in walking speed was observed between the groups ($p < 0.001$). Although both groups reported regular walking, the nature of physical activity may differ between them. While the non-volunteer group may engage in unstructured walking, formal volunteers may participate in more structured, task-oriented activities, which could contribute to maintaining or improving walking speed.

In line with previous research, physical activity and social engagement appear to play a critical role in successful aging (Finkenzerler et al., 2019; Tan et al., 2009). Slower walking speed has been associated with increased severity of cognitive impairment (McGough et al., 2013; Morris et al., 2016). Therefore, the better walking performance observed in the formal volunteer group may indicate a protective effect of structured activity on physical and cognitive health.

Loneliness is a subjective experience that may not always correspond to objective social isolation (Steptoe et al., 2013). While loneliness has been associated with poorer cognitive function (Boss et al., 2015), no significant difference was found between the groups in terms of living alone in this study. This suggests that factors beyond living arrangements may influence perceived loneliness.

Visual function has also been associated with cognitive performance. Studies have suggested that good visual acuity and the use of corrective lenses may have a protective effect against cognitive decline (Finger et al., 2014; Harrabi et al., 2015; Spierer et al., 2016). A study conducted on 1,032 individuals aged over 60 reported a significant association between myopia and cognitive dysfunction, independent of body mass index (BMI), income, education, and literacy levels (Ong et al., 2013). In the present study, no significant difference was found between the groups in terms of glasses use. It is possible that lifestyle factors, such as regular reading habits and adaptation to modern technologies (e.g., smartphone use), may contribute to maintaining visual and cognitive function in older adults.

In addition to the factors discussed above, one important consideration when interpreting the findings of this study is the difference in educational level between the groups. The formal volunteer group had significantly higher years of education compared to the non-volunteer group. Since education is a well-established determinant of cognitive reserve, this difference may have influenced cognitive outcomes and potentially masked any effect of volunteering on cognitive function. Therefore, the lack of a significant difference in cognitive function between groups should be interpreted with caution.

Although no significant difference in cognitive function was observed, the findings highlight that formal volunteering is associated with meaningful improvements in depression levels and physical performance. These results suggest that the benefits of volunteering in older adults may be more evident in psychological well-being and physical functioning rather than in cognitive outcomes, particularly in relatively healthy populations. Recent evidence suggests

that the benefits of volunteering in later life extend beyond physical health and may contribute to healthy aging through enhanced social participation, improved well-being, and maintenance of functional capacity. Matthews and Nazroo (2021) reported that volunteering after retirement was associated with improved well-being, while Chang et al. (2022) demonstrated positive associations between volunteering and self-reported health outcomes among community-dwelling older adults. These findings support the view that volunteering may serve as a valuable component of active and healthy aging strategies.

This study is among the few studies that simultaneously evaluate cognitive function, depression, and physical performance in relation to formal volunteering in older adults. Furthermore, it provides evidence from a Turkish population, where research on the health effects of volunteering remains limited.

Due to the cross-sectional design of this study, causal relationships cannot be established. Future longitudinal studies are needed to clarify whether volunteering leads to improved physical and psychological outcomes or whether healthier individuals are more likely to engage in volunteering activities.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, while no significant difference in cognitive function was observed between older adults engaged in formal volunteering and those who were not, volunteering was associated with lower levels of depression and better physical performance. These findings emphasize the importance of promoting volunteering opportunities as a potential strategy to support mental and physical well-being in older adults.

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Conflict of Interest:

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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